

Participant 17

SUMMARY KEYWORDS

team, test cases, missed, sprint, quality, testing, test, issues, work, requirement, happen, estimate, question, people, scrum master, initiative, project, case, effort, business

SPEAKERS

Participant 17, Researcher

Researcher 00:27

Good morning. Participant 17. Can you hear me?

Participant 17 00:37

Oh, hello. Hi, good morning.

Researcher 00:48

Okay, fantastic. Thanks for your time to do the interview today. I appreciate. I'm just going to briefly explain to you how the interview works. And we'll start the interview afterwards. Okay. So this is a research study, where I talk to quality assurance, and software developer working in Agile. And I'm trying to understand how do they work in an agile environment where admitting mistakes, bringing problem forward and talking about initiative taking initiative helps the agile team. So after doing the interviews, I will analyse the interviews, and I will propose conclusions from the study. So the interview works. I do have questions. I've already sent you some question in an email. Thanks for answering that I appreciate. And we will go through those answers. And they will ask question and we can discuss and feel free to add anything at any time. So it is quite fluid. It's not. It's we don't have to strictly follow the interview. As long as you have something to add within the topic, feel free to add it. So do you have any questions before we start?

Participant 17 02:17

I'm not actually had one and you answer that I thought of knowing what this project is actually about. And yes, you answered that.

Researcher 02:26

So okay, can we start with an introduction, a brief introduction about yourself briefly, maybe your education and experience?

Participant 17 02:39

Yes, sure. So for now, I'm working for [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] UK, and working as it is still here. And of course, we are working on agile environment and I have worked in waterfall model and methodology as well. I have minded as to short experience, to be precise is it's 9.7 years of experience completely into software testing. I had worked for some three energies. One task per one staminodes And a friend I was working for tech seven technologies all from Indian and UK companies. ICICI recertified VISTA. And I'm a bachelor of engineering we graduate in electronics and instrumentation that is my main course. And I'm planning to get my MBA.

Researcher 03:35

Okay, good luck with the MBA. It's a tough programme okay. What other methods do you use? Are you using Scrum in your counting?

Participant 17 03:51

Yes, sir. Yes.

Researcher 03:52

Okay. Can you take me briefly how do you use Scrum in your team?

Participant 17 03:58

Right. So, the project starts in this way, we will be having a workgroup call from the business analyst and the client to all the stakeholders from there be part of testing team start a we create escapes from asset and oh we do appear very informally. So, that is the place that we will record this peer review stuff. Anyway. We provided our test cases for clients and the peer reviews and then our test environment setup and test execution start in between we will be preparing our test data aspect. So this declaration has been started so all of the requested for test execution will be done this part. So now we can say test execution. So based on the task assigned, we carry on with our test execution and defect reporting. We are using HP ALM, quality centre and JIRA for task and sprints management tools and your defect tracking tools. So, once that is done we start off with our migration phase or the last week of course. So, this is basically a cold mix this is basically for four weeks into the fourth week could be gently migration one and also we will be supporting automation team in our sprint to be the sound happens. So we will be preparing for the next plane. Because it goes as for me as in pattern.

Researcher 05:35

Okay, fantastic tech. So how big is your team?

Participant 17 05:44

In testing team we have around 20 members for this particular project. We have six members in QAs. So the Scrum teams have some 22 members,

Researcher 05:57

Okay, that's a big team, isn't it? Yes. Are you cross functional? So, you work with the developer, the product owner and the business are all you are separated from each function?

Participant 17 06:16

Yes, pertaining to that particular release or spring? We are cross functional, we work with every role.

Researcher 06:23

Okay, how long have you been working together as a team? Or is it new team?

Participant 17 06:31

I kind of mix it we have a new members recruited as well. So it kind of means that maybe some 10 to 12 members? They are they're working in this force for some past two years. The rest of them are new to this project not to attend except for private

Researcher 06:51

Okay. And what type of software do you develop?

Participant 17 06:59

Here it is banking application and basically so, we are solving for [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] for now, and we have been serving for the [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity]. So, this is a basically banking application wherein we can manage all banking related stuffs from both banker and client. Always.

Researcher 07:23

Okay, fantastic. During this conversation, we will be talking about software quality, right? So, software quality is defined in many ways. And people and teams can have slightly different definitions. But in this study, we use a definition from the ISO standards, and I'll read it to you and we can discuss it afterwards. So, the definition states software quality is the degree to which the system satisfies the stated and implied needs of its various stakeholders and thus provide value. This ISO model also covers some non functional characteristic like performance compatibility, usability, reliability, security, maintainability and portability. So, do you agree with this definition? Or would you disagree?

Participant 17 08:30

Yes, I agree. Basically, the ISO definition is meeting stakeholders needs. So that is the common definition. So what comes under these needs are the categories of testing in terms of performance in terms of reliability, usability, all those types come under that needs term. So basically, satisfying the needs of the client and checking if the product is working as for the satisfaction is basically it is I mean the quality.

Researcher 09:05

Okay, fantastic. That's a good definition. Thank you. I've sent you some questions on the email, and I'll explain one term. One word we will be using in this interview and in my assessment, and before I give you my assessment of the question you've sent and we will continue the discussion. So I do believe from the questions you've asked that your team is highly a safe working environment. What do we mean by a highly safe work environment? It is it means we mean that the work environment provides a sense of security from repercussions. So you feel that it's okay to admit mistakes, you feel that it's okay to propose initiative and discuss problem, there is a sense of confidence in the team that it's okay. And they will not embarrass or reject or punish someone for speaking up. So people are confidence to

speak up and to say what they have to say. And this confidence comes from a mutual respect and trust among the team member. So the question, the answers you provided indicate that you that the team is a highly safe work environment. Would you agree, strongly disagree, disagree, neutral, agree, or strongly agree of this assessment?

Participant 17 10:53

That depends on the team. Actually, I'm the team lead and actually for my site, that depends. So for the team and working with I agree is new initiatives can be done, all the support can be addressed, all the issues can be addressed, everything happens in writing. But again, that depends on the need and the temperament of the team and QAs. So if we have any deviations among the systems, of course, we won't be able to do that.

Researcher 11:29

So talking about your team, I mean, the answers you provided is about your current team, right. So we will be talking about your team and the context of your team. So you agree that is, it is a highly safe work environment, right?

Participant 17 11:49

Yes, it definitely it is.

Researcher 11:50

So when you see the band, what do you need from your own experience, sometimes it doesn't happen.

Participant 17 11:58

Yes, because if you are facing any issues, if you are facing any hiccup, that has to be brought up at a very earlier stage of the Scrum and in the sprint at least, if we have say for example, we have four weeks sprint and startup somewhere if I'm bringing that issue during my third week, that won't work obviously. So that has to be brought up during first or second weeks for which we could be easily we'll be able to address that issue. So that is one part second part is during the middle of second week and third we will be at our highest point you'll be in an artistic usual case we will be having much time to address other issues, but we will be running with our task. So at that time, if something is being brought that would be a question that depends on the person's availability. So everything could be solved and everything could be addressed if at all that is being brought up at the earliest stage it is not nope it is completely yes it is no during the middle of this.

Researcher 13:11

So your current team seems to be a strongly safe work environment where people bring initiative problems etc. So what in your opinion what's made it a safe work environment? In your opinion? What's made it this way? The team what has helped the team to be the way it is now?

Participant 17 13:40

Um, you mean to ask what makes our team to take up initiatives?

Researcher 13:45

Yes.

Participant 17 13:48

Um, see, we have a we have a team of mixer members. And it was funny because yes of experience, I have a manager of some blood vessels, I officious as well. So this is a government authority. And this is a plan to set up. So management part would be taken care by the by my family, and all the execution reporting, those steps will be taken care by me. And we have freshers to pick up initiatives. So their mindsets are very, very fiery, they can't take up any new things, because they have that kind of mind. So all these new issues can be taken up with those members, with me mentoring them, and I have a need to make them meet. So this is the kind of setup by which we take up initiatives and we do experimenting.

Researcher 14:48

Great, thank you. I'll move to the next question I've sent in the email and we can start the discussion of these questions. And thanks for sending the answers. prior to the interview. So the first question says if you make mistakes in your team, it is often held against you. And the answer says no. In terms of delivery, I work as a create tester and mistakes done by any of the member would be held against you the key a team in common. And dividual pointing happens during resource validation lesson learned phase on the key a retrospective. Can you explain a little bit what happens when people admit mistakes or when mistakes happen?

Participant 17 15:39

Yes, so at representing to me again, while representing your team, you won't own any mistakes or in a single person, I guess it's because we don't do that. So it is actually the output, if at all something is missed, it is activities miss if something has happened wonderfully is waiting for this how we operate. Again, if this is being introduced, we will be facing many misses during our further sprints. So we don't blame we own the issue together as a team. How we handle this by having lessons learned retrospective meetings create from QSR, we have two steps. These are dedicated to what we have learned and how we can avoid it in the future. At that time, we know what has been missed and who has missed that. So we will be having one on one discussions with them to come up with those. Those missings we do that. So the individual pointing wouldn't happen within the team neither informally nor formally during the prospecting rounds. So while representing too late to other teams, we won't hold any issues against a single person, this is just how we work.

Researcher 16:56

So collectively as a team, you take accountability for the mistakes. That's what you're saying.

Participant 17 17:03

Yes, it is good.

Researcher 17:06

Okay, so how does it help the team when you do that?

Participant 17 17:12

We don't, we don't let down anyone. Formally, with back when other teams, if you have any issues with our resources, we do that within a team. And within [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] we have, we have kind of taking centre of excellence through a QA Centre of Excellence. We can have our issues raised, we can have the trainings scheduled with this part if you are missing something. So this helped me build up over it. So if something is being delivered and missing something during that, that is a team's missed in collecting as well.

Researcher 17:57

So do you have an example where somebody made a mistake, and he or she came forward and share the mistakes? And how the team dealt with it? And what happened?

Participant 17 18:13

Yeah, it generally happens not particularly with my Agile team recently, in almost all the projects, what happens? So we would miss some, some functionalities we would have to test, we would have missed that. So if that comes up, we will have three kinds of checks here. The first check is if we have test cases. We have two games have successfully if we are missing some functionality. During testing, we will check whether it is our test case, if something is being covered in test case and if it is being missed in testing. So that is an issue to be addressed. So, we don't have that in test case itself, we go for the specification document. If the particular functionality which is being missed, we will check if that is given as part of the specification or requirement if that is there, it is missed. If that is not there, we will reach out to business analysts and stakeholders who at that point as a requirement. And that comes as a requirement for the next sprint. So this is one but if everything is negative, if something important is missing from our side, we create that as a backlog item. And we address that in the next week. So this how it works.

Researcher 19:53

So how this approach which is quite a healthy approach to managing mistakes and issues helps the quality or improving the quality of your software.

Participant 17 20:07

It was a good question. No.

Researcher 20:11

No, I'm asking the follow up questions. Should I repeat the question? Yeah. So this approach to managing mistakes and dealing with mistakes, which is quite a healthy approach to dealing with mistakes. How does it help improving the quality of the software or your work as a software quality assurance team?

Participant 17 20:50

Of course, yes. Okay. It does help quality. First, the person won't be repeating the same mistake again. So that is one way of improving quality. The second thing is, if at all some something is being missed, we will directly go to the requirement document to check if that missed has been recorded as part of the requirement for that would again raise our quality if, if the functionality we have missed is not as part of

the requirement document, we would ask our stakeholders to do that, which would increase the product's quality. So the third checkers, we do regression part. During the regression, of course, we would be coming up with a mystery functionality. So that could be covered. So this improves quality, even if you are missing something.

Researcher 21:47

Okay, great. Thanks. Thanks a lot for the example that was very interesting. Yeah. I appreciate sharing the example. I moved to the next question. Which says member of your team can bring up problem and tough issues? Your answer says yes, any problem issue could be brought up? And would we address the only condition? Is that the problem to be exposed as early as possible? Can you explain to me how does it work in the team how people brings problem and when people brings problem? How do how do you deal with it as a team?

Participant 17 22:30

Yes, if, for example, I had a member, two plus years of experience member she has, she doesn't have that much hands on all the product. So she wanted a training, she had been given a proper format, and that is fine. But during this sprint, she has been assigned with some tasks, some functionalities to be tested. And she wasn't aware of that particular functionality. The functionality was to test the financial terms of the portfolio of events portfolio, she has to test the performance of everyone's portfolio, but this is different. And she isn't aware of the formulas being used to calculate the performance of their particular portfolio. So this is the issue this area, which happened for us. So she wrote test cases, you know, where everything is done, but during the test execution part, she isn't aware of the formulas. So she came up asking for help to test that particular functionality. We were completely bad and the viewer not into support at that time. So if she had come up with this particular problem during the first week, or the first half of certainly, this would have been addressed properly. She came in between the sprints. So we were not able to support that much. So we had to extend our time. No compromise in quality that is for sure. So we work between nine and six. So to address her issue and to make to ensure the quality we were working 11:30 That day to address her issues. And the next day she was preparing and she was continuing with that as execution. So this was happened. We don't want that to happen any time. So any issues will be addressed. Provided they the issues to be brought up during the very initial stage.

Researcher 24:39

How did it help her this constructive approach to help in her and did it help and how it did help her. Did you see any improvement?

Participant 17 24:56

Yes, she won't be bringing up this kind of stuff. During the middle of the sprint, I mean, working with that for other sprints, we noticed that any issues she had to be bringing up in very early state of spirit itself, but one for that is resolved. Part two is that we did a shadow banning, like, she has to sit with other resources to know what exactly is B, and what exactly is happening the product to just get a handle on it. So she has been given with a 50% of her time for tasks, proper regular task per person and the rest 50% would be dedicated to learn the product and our processes. So by three sprints, she picked it up and she did it in her own way.

Researcher 25:48

So that's interesting, you allowed her time to improve, you did give her a leeway to 50% of her time to improve and prepare for the next sprints. That's very interesting.

Participant 17 26:02

Yeah, that helps our quality as well as the team's improvement. So we needed that at that time. Also, we had a possibility to do that. So we propose to do that. And we have done it successfully actually. She also became confident and coming forward with questions and suggestions

Researcher 26:18

Do you have another example where somebody brought a quality related problem? Something is missing in your processes and influencing the quality of the software or the level of testing? And how did you go about it? If you have an example specific like that, I would appreciate?

Participant 17 26:41

Ah, yes. So the first thing is the sprint plan should be happen very possible. For example, we have sales behind some 20 items, this would require one week to test for example. And the estimate should be for one week only not for three or four days, we should not, we should not cram the test estimate. So that could affect the quality in a very significant way. So we don't allow that. For if it is if the testing purpose, one week of time estimate should be for one week, Monday. So this is how this how we plan. Here we had quality issues because of this. Due to the release, I mean, the release was very hectic. And we had to complete all the requirements of what we did was we just we just created test cases for the requirements only. So the requirements been covered, everything was ready. But the problematic part is that we didn't do any business testing, real time testing layer one test cases should have been derived and those test cases could have been tested, even if it is not part of the requirement. So because of this time cramping, we just created distances for whatever the requirement is, and we completed it successfully. The problem is we missed the business cases, reopen test cases, user perspective is cases we must do that.

Researcher 28:18

So what happened? Sorry, yeah, continue. Sorry to interrupt.

Participant 17 28:24

That's okay. So it happened in real time. [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] came back with few issues on that. But of course, we had we were able to defend, because those are not part of the requirement document. We were able to defend, but the thing is as equity we should have reread those cases, we should have tested business cases already because of the timestamp and estimate we happen to do. So as a solution, we don't do such a stink such a cramp is. So if it is to request one week of time, the estimate is it for one week, what is it is not three or four days, it is for seven days. So this is how we resolve that issue.

Researcher 29:10

So how did you deal with the situation as a team and how did you learn from it?

Participant 17 29:18

As I said we had no issues formally, because we haven't missed anything from the requirement document. The issue was with the business scenario, which is not very formal, that should have been banned from liquidity. And that should have been recorded as part of requirement document as well. So we were not in a problematic situation formally. But from QA side, we made a decision to cover up all these things in in forthcoming sprints. So the estimates were the proper the buffer so that we can test more than achieve better quality.

Researcher 30:02

So, moving forward, how this situation helps you afterwards? I mean, in the future, did your attitude or processes have changed as a result of this experience?

Participant 17 30:22

Yes, we have some we have some estimates, for example, per day per person A is cases when it's used. So this is our per day count. This business cases may not have is involved for for, say four set of 16 test cases, for one person, we would require two days. You understand this?

Participant 17 31:11

For example, say we have 16 test cases and one resource allotted as per the estimate and standards, one person could execute a test cases per day. So, the estimate is two this year, but we don't do estimate for two days, we do it for two and a half days, that half a day is for the business and reopen testing exploratory testing phase. So, the pattern of testers teammate has changed and due to that the quality of product got improved and also the QA teams quality coding, so what we do with it

Researcher 31:50

thank you very much. That's a very good example I appreciate I move to the next question. People in your team sometimes the reject other for being different, you said not at all all members are ready to take up things from people who are different they feel change and assume scheduled impact. What do you mean by they feel change?

Participant 17 32:23

It was it was in a different manner? Not all the members my answer was not all the members

Researcher 32:33

Okay. Okay. All right. Yeah.

Participant 17 32:39

For example, I'll tell you what happened within my team, we have a separate automation team. The automation stuffs How it works is they do backlog items for example, and in sprint six, they will be automating sprint two items. So, for them to reach sprint, six for automation, we will be travelling in sprint for functional, so, the summit is happening. What I suggested was to create or to I had a proposal of doing in sprint automation means the tasks of this sprint and the items of the sprint could be automated in coming sprint itself. I had this idea I proposed this idea why I came up with this is because

in the next sprint, we will be doing a regression testing of the previous one if that is been automated, that regression effort will be complicated for manual. So that was one idea I came up with but that didn't work out because they were not ready to organise other automation thing for this. So, a fear of change is this basically they have to they have to reach out to the QA cod team to come up with this plan to organise a new automation setup so they are not ready for that. So that didn't work out. So this is one best example from my sorry.

Researcher 34:14

Thanks for that good example. I appreciate we would move to the next question which is lets me pick up on that thing. So, if somebody has a different way of working or approaching a task, so he or she are not rejected by the team, they are always welcome even though if their style of doing things are different, right?

Participant 17 34:42

Yes. Okay. Yes, the delivery has to happen on time. That is the only condition.

Researcher 34:51

So as long as they do their job in efficient manners and they perform and they deliver, it's fine to do there. To be different and to do their task in a different way, right?

Participant 17 35:03

Yes, they can experiment they can have their own style in doing the job. So we can learn from them as well that is not an issue at all. The only condition is that delivery has to happen.

Researcher 35:16

Okay, fantastic. So that's brings me to the next question, which is a good introduction to the next question. You mentioned a good work they can experiment that's means they can take initiative and try new things, etc. So, do you what's made people what encourage people in your team to take initiative and experiment

Participant 17 35:46

If we don't work be in a relationship base, we are not very formal. So that is the one basic thing we have good rapport among working for you if I have any, any editing or feedback or something to be true from other person, I would follow that I also I have, I have the comfort to tell my opinions above other person's asking every purposes, this rapport is basically thing which we have to improve or to take up new initiatives. So this is one part. The second thing is as I told we have mixer experienced people. So if a fresher comes up with a new idea, it's me feel that works out we do that as experiment and we take it as initiative and we go on with that idea. So, the, the organising this thing is the second part. The third part is we just wanted our ability to showcase ourselves. Among other we have a CV under tool in case you were here we have 20 plus VR games working for different projects. So, to showcase our team among those other things, we do this

Researcher 37:09

Do you have an example where yourself or a team member took initiative or experimented and it did help your quality assurance processes or it did help to improve the testing or the software quality?

Participant 17 37:30

Okay, in terms of process, we did the one thing that thing is walkthroughs computing. So, this is we do it as we work through what happens yes, we create test cases from the requirement document we do everything and from the creating we propose the walkthrough to the stakeholders to ensure if everything has been covered and all the business cases have been taught to ensure this we give a walkthrough from creating for other stakeholders. So, this improved our process also the quality of the product in a very efficient way. For example, say developers would have missed something we would have written a particular test case for that miss that will be addressed in that in this call. So we are in it we're working with from our stakeholders stakeholders which was very efficient, we had a change in process and this process in and in this process have been recorded to the company [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity] itself. So this is one part second part is creating a face for business district. So as you say, if the estimate is for two days, we do estimate for two and a half is and that profit is for the business district. So this has improved our product quality and deliveries quality to a large extent.

Researcher 39:00

Okay, great. Thank you. That was another good example. I move to the next question, which is almost in the same line as the previous questions. I think we discussed it already, but I will I will repeat it for the sake of the interview. So it says that no one on my team would deliberately act in a way that undermines my effort. You said yes, all the member put that effort. If someone's effort is higher they are recognise mine is a transparent team and mate would put higher effort to prove themselves instead of acting to undermine my efforts. So I do have a few questions regarding this answer which is very nice. What's drive people to put effort and As you infer size a lot on people put in effort and they are recognised for the effort, what to drive people, what motivates people in your team to put efforts in the first place.

Participant 17 40:14

The first thing is, we are being recognised unconditionally. So that is the first thing, everyone will be recognised in my game based on their efforts. So if our efforts are genuine will be taken next. So that is the most important factor which drives us to do that. First, the second thing this, we will be easily predicted to the client, which may not happen in most of the teams see in decline call would happen between the project lead and testing, not the team members. So what our team members does, that would be projected to decline via it just doesn't happen here. Each and every team member who participate in the bench call, if at all, we have some issues, or if at all, we have some opinions from our side, we could directly talk with them. So that is the second part. So to have some content to talk with client, I have to do something for myself. So that effort could be good from our site, to have a good rapport with clients and to show off our opinions and show off our words. So these are the factors which delivers to put on more effort.

Researcher 41:32

Okay, great. And when people put extra effort, do you think it helps your performance? And does it help to improve the quality of the software you're testing?

Participant 17 41:47

Of course, yes. Say actually, I can, I can draw some 100 percent for a requirement? Yeah, I don't have to go upon I mean, I don't have to go beyond. So, putting effort, I would go to the related documents of those steps and I will come up with other set of test cases for that particular requirement. If at all, I think if covering the requirement is fine, I would start with 100 test cases only. But I wanted the quality to be improved and I wanted new issues to be found. So, I work on the related documents and I would come up with another set of test cases apart from this. So this is how we could fit so this small example this will be put effort. So this is this design base we put effort in this way. So during test execution, we do some random testing, exploratory testing, we do everything. So to this how we put our extra effort.

Researcher 42:47

Thank you very much. That was a good example. And the last questions and we can discuss afterwards. The last question states working with a member of my team, my unique skills and talents are values and utilised and your answer was yes, my unique skills and our valued no one know when it comes to utilisation, the project and delivery schedule would have to demand our unique skill which does doesn't happen all the time. So first, how does it make you feel when you you're you feel or you find that your skills are valued in your team?

Participant 17 43:36

Okay, so during our free time, during non sprint time, we have many trainings here. So we involve ourselves in finding and we develop our skills. Based on the skills we develop, we will be we can have it recorded during our appraisal hype and that would be valued at specifications to trainings all those steps will be valued but need not be utilised because the project has to demand that for example, I have learned the Tosca tool testing automation tool by myself. But my project doesn't have so called they use Selenium. So the thing is, if at all some projects come with it also I will recognise now are being valued, but my spirit is not being utilised. So that is what I say for example, if I'm doing MBA that could do that could have no use in my case. Because whatever the education and skill I have is more than enough for what I'm working. So with my MBA, I will have to go on to the other team and other opportunities. So my MBA will be valued but may not be utilised for the for what I'm interested in.

Researcher 44:56

That's quite normal. Sometimes we work unlike a lot of people work for teams that they are over skilled, but you still can enjoy working on a team even if you are over skilled or your skills are not 100% utilised

Participant 17 45:15

Yet that happens very naturally that the product has to demand a skill. So, if we have people without the particular skill for which the product is demanding, of course, we would employ them for timing and we would make them skills.

Researcher 45:33

When you when people in your team feel that their skills are utilised and they put effort and they are engaged positively with their task? Do you think it helps improve the quality in some sense?

Participant 17 45:55

Oh, yes, we do financial calculation. So, from working for banking company, we do financial calculations. Yes, for those financial calculations, one should be very handy with the Excel spreadsheet. So, if I'm skilled with that, the calculations which could take some one hour for other person, possibly person, it could take only 10 minutes. So, this is how we improve the quality of the product with that particular skill. So, this is just one example which case yet, because we do many financial calculations, which involve lots of formulas, lots of year ending calculation, two steps for that part, Excel scale, the person could do that better. So, that depends on the requirement, mapping with that particular step.

Researcher 46:54

Yeah, I agree. That's Participant 17, I'm very happy with these examples. Thank you very much for sharing those good examples. Before I conclude, do you like to add anything in this topic? We've been discussing something I didn't ask or something you feel like it's important to share with me or or to add to any things we have discussed.

Participant 17 47:24

Yes, I have I have something to share for your research. Yes. We do not follow almost all the terms come terms we have scrum master. The part of Scrum Master is that he has to pitch every department or every team so this is the part of Scrum Master for that, then scrum master should be technically skilled. Technically, not is compatible a lot. So if, let's say if I'm saying for recording this particular part, I would refer to as the scrum master has to know that this part to take only one master has to know that so that is completely missing in my team. So the scrum master should be capable it quickly. And Ill management was so so that is one that is one recommendation from my side.

Researcher 48:33

So do you think Sorry to interrupt? Do you think that the scrum master should be also technically knowledgeable of the type of work you do? Or?

Participant 17 48:41

Yes, yes, of course. Yes. At least, at least with higher levels. Okay. See, I can I can say this testing would take four days. But the actual testing would take only two days.

Researcher 48:56

So otherwise, he or she wouldn't understand what's happening, right?

Participant 17 49:00

Correct. Is not master should know about backpack in terms of estimate and what the second thing is a scrum master has to organise people as per the projects that will say it, see my party would prefer some particular skill, but because of the resources available in my resource pool, they would pull someone into this project, who is activity differently skilled, I won't say nonskid. They will be skilled in a

different way. But just for the requirement, resource purpose to show the build up to the client. They will pull up some differently skilled resources into our teams that should not happen. That can happen in waterfall because waterfall can have three to six months of delivery time. We can bring that resource posture so that could happen in waterfall. but that should not happen in Agile pattern because the maximum, we'll be having only four to eight weeks. So within that week for differently speak person you will have to train and we will have to get them delivered is not that is impossible. So that should not happen. That is happening in [deleted to preserve the researcher/participant anonymity].

Researcher 50:20

So, how about the product owner? Do you think that the product owner also need to have some level of technical knowledge, otherwise, he or she wouldn't be able to communicate and understand the technicalities of your job.

Participant 17 50:38

Um, no, he, he or she doesn't want to know the technical difficulty of the job, but he has to know the technicality of the product. Because I can I can work in my own ways too, knowing my style of work is of no use for the product manager. But doing the product in and out is a compulsory skill for the product owner. In terms of technical depth of management, business, everything.

Researcher 51:11

So, when the scrum master lacks this, this technical understanding, from your experience, what does happen?

Participant 17 51:22

Okay. But it's coming up with some issue in code. The code is because of the environment, I mean, the issues because of the environment. My scrum master had no idea regarding whom to reach out on this issue. So we had issues with code that is fine. He actually get you on making, the very next step is he or she is technically skilled, the next the next minute, you will be litigated on the team to have this resort. But he had no idea to reach. I mean, for the team to reach on this list in this way to bridge people, we ask to know the impact of every everything upon other teams. So this is what I'm expecting. This is how, at least at this level of technicality he should have.

Researcher 52:23

Otherwise, he would then know how to coordinate and how to address the team issues.

Participant 17 52:29

If he would let team members to talk, instead of posting, so that should not happen. If that happens, we will be blaming other teams. So if I'm missing something I would play on the telephone. It would be blatant on the tape. So this, this process would be this process would slow down. And again, this master has to have that poll, and he or she should know, which is impacting the other identity. So he or she should have

Researcher 53:01

Yeah, yes, I agree. You mentioned another things I'd like to use to help me to understand further. You said you don't use Scrum or agile as per the book. It is normal, a lot of people nobody does, what's other deviation or differences from the books you don't follow?

Participant 17 53:28

Right. So, we have we have for example, we have a digit leakage ratios, we have gone down burn up charts. So those terms has to be used in the project, it has some purpose involved in it. So we don't do that. Because of that you're not knowing how much effect we are missing. If something is being missed, we are taking it in an authentic way saying that we can have it addressed as a backlog or habit address as an excuse. During this if we have breakout. I mean, I mean, those kind of racy charts if you have that in the current sprint itself. We will know what we have missed and what all the efforts we have to put on to that you will be doing that. Just because we're not going to the books. We can have this managed as backlog or others to I don't want that to happen.

Researcher 54:30

I agree with you. Yes. Thanks for sharing those details. I really appreciate that. Is there any things? Any question for me or any things you'd like to add before we conclude?

Participant 17 54:49

I have just heard this dispatch on everything I face. Except all the best. I have nothing to share with you.

Researcher 54:58

Okay, thanks, Participant 17. I really appreciate and I like the example and I thank you a lot for sharing those example I appreciate and we'll stay in touch. Okay.

Participant 17 55:11

Sure.

Researcher 55:13

Yes. Have a good day. Have a good afternoon. Bye.

Participant 17 55:17

Thank you so much.

Researcher 55:20

Thanks for your time to you bye